

Diverse ions : Aqueous solutions of other metal ions were prepared from nitrates, chlorides or sulphates. Solutions of anions were made from the sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. A few drops of a suitable acid was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the stock solution containing 5.0 to 25.0 mg of bismuth (III), sodium potassium tartrate (3 g) solution was added. It was diluted to 200 ml and the pH was adjusted between 6.2 and 7.2 with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.0M) solution. The mixture was heated to 40°-50° and ethanolic solution of the reagent (0.21 to 0.30 g) was added dropwise with stirring. The creamy white precipitate formed was digested on hot (65°-70°) water bath for 25 to 40 mins with occasional stirring. The complex was filtered hot on a weighed gooch crucible No. 3, washed with hot (60°) water and weighed as $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ after drying at 110°-120° for 2 hrs. The metal content of the complex was obtained using a factor 0.2356.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions : Calcium, strontium and barium did not interfere. Separation of bismuth (III) from magnesium (II), arsenic (III), antimony (III), molybdenum (VI) and tungsten (VI) was possible following the procedure described above. However, 1.0 g of citric acid was added to effect separation of bismuth (III) from beryllium (II), lead (II), lanthanum (III), thorium (IV) and uranium (VI). The influence of manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II), zinc (II), cadmium (II), mercury (II) and palladium (II) was removed by adding citric acid (1.0 g) and sodium cyanide (1.0 g). Reasonable amounts of fluoride, phosphate and oxalate did not interfere with the precipitation of bismuth (III). The pH was maintained between 6.2 and 6.5 while effecting all the above separations.

Properties and composition of the complex : The creamy white bismuth (III)-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine complex melted with decomposition at 186° ± 1°. The complex was insoluble in hot (75°) water, fairly soluble in acetone, diethylether and acetic acid but slightly soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and pet-ether. It was found to be stable to (about 5N) mineral acids for few hours. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ in which bismuth to ligand ratio is 1 : 3 (Found : C, 56.61; H, 4.02; N, 4.77%. Calc : C, 56.82; H, 4.05; N, 4.73%).

It was found that the precipitation of bismuth (III) commenced at pH 5.1 and was quantitative in the range 6.0-8.0 and at least 125 mg excess of the reagent, in addition to the theoretical amount, was necessary for the complete precipitation of the bismuth complex.

Results showed that 5 to 25 mg of bismuth (III) could be determined accurately. Diverse ions such as Mg^{2+} , As^{3+} or Sb^{3+} (35 mg); La^{3+} or UO_2^{2+} (28 mg); MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , Zn^{2+} or Hg^{2+} (25 mg); Mn^{2+} or Co^{2+} (20 mg); Be^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Th^{4+} or Ni^{2+} (15 mg); Cd^{2+} (16 mg), Pd^{2+} (12 mg), Cu^{2+} (10 mg), F^- (250 mg),

PO_4^{3-} (500 mg) or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (1000 mg) produced no influence on the precipitation of 10.16 mg of bismuth (III).

Interference : Disodium-EDTA, thioglycolic acid and large amount of fluoride interfered with the precipitation of bismuth (III) with N-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine.

Precision and Accuracy : The average error for 25 determinations of 5.0 to 25.0 mg of bismuth (III) in 200 ml was found to be ±0.5%.

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Constituents of *Seseli indicum*

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SESELI INDICUM, Wight & Arnold (*Umbelliferae*), grows generally in the plains of India. The seeds are medicinally very important¹. They act as an anthelmintic, stimulant, carminative and stomachic and are used for other purposes. Bose and Guha^{2a} isolated two coumarins, while a third was obtained by Spath *et al.*^{2b} The seeds also contain a fatty oil³ and an essential oil^{4,5}.

In view of the medicinal importance and utility of the drug a systematic chemical investigation of the dry and powdered yellowish seeds of the plant was carried out through solvent extraction, since no work appeared to have been done so far in this direction. The different extracts of the seeds obtained with petrol (60°-80°; 3.0%), benzene (4.5%), and alcohol (5.0%) were thoroughly examined. Isolation and characterisation of a number of products for the first time is reported in the present communication.

The pet.- ether extract was treated with aq. KOH (10%) and the alkali-soluble part (1.0%) on chromatography (silica gel) and crystallisation (methanol) gave a product, m.p. 83°-85° which emitted fluorescence when exposed to u.v. light. It was identified as suberosin by m.m.p. and Co-T.L.C. with an authentic specimen of the coumarin. Further elution with benzene gave bergapten (m.p.

187°–188°), while elution with chloroform afforded seselin (m.p. 119°–120°) and isopimpinellin (m.p. 151°–153°). Those were also identified by m.m.p. and Co-T.L.C. with authentic specimens of the respective compounds.

The neutral part of the above extract (1.8%) on saponification, steam-distillation and repeated chromatography (alumina) yielded three products: A, B and C. Elution with petrol (40°–60°) gave a colourless product A, m.p. 68°–70°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBR}}$ 2900, 2830, 1470, 1375, 720 and 710 cm^{-1} . For final confirmation the product was subjected to G.L.C. analysis. It was thereafter found to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes composed of the series C_{23} – C_{35} ; mainly:

Heptacosane (C_{27} , 6.4%); Triacontane (C_{30} , 3.3%); Octacosane (C_{28} , 3.3%); Hentriacontane (C_{31} , 24.8%); Nonacosane (C_{29} , 41.2%); Tritriacontane (C_{33} , 16.9%).

accompanied by minor quantities of dotriacontane and pentatriacontane along with traces of the rest. The result confirms the general findings⁶ that the odd numbered alkanes predominate in plants.

Elution with petrol- C_6H_6 (1 : 1) and crystallisation from MeOH-CHCl_3 gave a crystalline solid (B, T.L.C.-homogeneous) giving positive Liebermann-Burchard and tetranitromethane tests; m.p. 137°–138°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} -33^\circ$; ν_{max} 3570 and 1653 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 126°–127°. This was identified as β -sitosterol by m.p., m.m.p., Co-T.L.C. and superimposable I.R. spectra. The acetate also did not show any depression in m.m.p. with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate.

Further elution with benzene afforded another compound (C, T.L.C./adsorbent silicagel AgNO_3 -homogeneous), m.p. 153°–155°, $[\alpha]_D +30^\circ$; M^+ 412, also giving positive Liebermann-Burchard test and yellow colour with T.N.M. It gave an acetate (T.L.C./adsorbent AgNO_3 -homogeneous), m.p. 135°–138°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +20^\circ$; a benzoate, m.p. 160°–163°, and the 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 231°–233° (Found: N, 4.07%; Calc. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$: N, 4.62%). On further investigations and comparison of the data with literature it has been found to be a new sterol, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ (Found: C, 48.00%; H, 11.89%; Calc. C, 84.40%; H, 11.72%), and has been designated as 'Indosterol'. It contains two double bonds and three vinylic protons, and belongs to stigmastane series. On the basis of various physico-chemical studies it has been assigned the structure (I) carrying a significant feature: C_{9-11} ethylenic linkage. The neutral

part indicated the presence of campesterol also by G.L.C. analysis. The benzene extract of the seeds also yielded the above coumarins and the sterols.

The alcoholic extract of the seeds was treated in three different manners and thereafter tested for the

identification of sugars, amino-acids and carboxylic acids by co-paper chromatography⁷. The results indicated the presence of glucose, rhamnose; alanine, leucine, serine, valine, asparagine, threonine; and citric, succinic and oxalic acids.

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Hydrazone and Pyrazoline Derivatives from Mesityl Oxide

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THE phenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide—an α , β -unsaturated ketone has not yet been isolated although the pyrazoline from it has been obtained. Auwers and Kreuder¹ have isolated the *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone and have cyclised it to the pyrazoline using hot acetic acid, a known reagent for the conversion of hydrazones to pyrazolines². The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide although easily prepared³⁻⁵ had not been cyclised. The